

Investigation of Soret and Dufour Effects on Chemically Reacting Free Convective Fluid Flowing Over a Vertical Plate Along with Viscous Dissipation Using the Laplace Adomian Decomposition Method

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ABSTRACT:

This study comprehensively analyses heat and mass transfer phenomena in a chemically reacting free convective fluid flow along a vertically moving plate. The flow is influenced by thermo-diffusion, diffusion-thermo, and viscous dissipation effects. To simplify the analysis, scaling group analysis and appropriate similarity transformations are used to transform the governing equations into nonlinear ordinary differential equations. These equations are then solved using a combination of Laplace transform and the Adomian decomposition method. The study conducts a parametric investigation to explore the impact of various control parameters on the dimensionless velocity, temperature, and concentration profiles. The parameters considered include the Prandtl number, Schmidt number, Eckert number, chemical reaction parameter, Soret parameter, Dufour parameter, solutal Grashof number, and thermal Grashof number. These parameters are depicted graphically and analysed quantitatively. The results reveal that an increase in the Schmidt number leads to a decrease in velocity and concentration profiles while temperature varies monotonically. Elevating the Eckert number enhances velocity and temperature profiles, with a slight decrease in concentration profiles. A rise in the Prandtl number decreases the temperature profile, with minimal effects on velocity and concentration profiles. Increasing the solutal Grashof number decreases temperature and concentration profiles, whereas the thermal Grashof number is directly proportional to the velocity profile. An increase in the Dufour parameter boosts velocity and temperature profiles while reducing the concentration profile. The presence of the Soret parameter increases velocity and concentration profiles but decreases the temperature profile. This study aims to enhance comprehension of the complex interactions within flow characteristics, providing valuable insights into the fundamental mechanisms of such systems. It also highlights their potential applications in various engineering and industrial processes.

Keywords: Soret, Dufour, viscous Dissipation, chemical reaction, Scaling Group Analysis.

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INTRODUCTION

Free convection occurs in fluids when temperature changes cause density differences, leading to fluid movement. When a fluid is heated, it expands and rises due to lower density, while cooler fluid contracts and sinks due to higher density. This natural circulation creates flow patterns within the fluid, enabling heat transfer without the need for external mechanisms [1-4]. In free convection,

buoyancy forces driven by density imbalances from temperature gradients govern heat transfer. As a result, warmer fluid rises near a heat source, carrying heat away, while cooler fluid moves toward the heat source to replace it. This continuous movement generates convective currents that enhance heat transfer efficiency across various systems and environments [5-7]

Free convection fluid flow is a common occurrence in natural phenomena, including atmospheric circulation, ocean currents, food processing, and geothermal systems. Its practical applications in engineering, such as cooling systems, solar collectors, and chemical reactors, play a crucial role in enhancing heat transfer processes and system efficiency. Understanding the principles governing free convection fluid flow is essential for designing effective heat transfer systems, predicting fluid dynamics, and optimizing thermal regulation in various industrial and environmental settings Srinivasa et al. [8]. Additionally, the significance of free convection extends to environmental processes like ocean currents, atmospheric circulation, and climate patterns. Research on free convection fluid flow is vital for developing sustainable and efficient technologies, as well as for anticipating and mitigating the impacts of natural phenomena. Over the past two decades, researchers have delved into this field, exploring effects like viscous dissipation, chemical reactions, and Soret and Dufour effects using a variety of methods, from analytical to numerical approaches Hoshiyar et al. [9]

In the study of free convection fluid flow over a vertical plate, the significant impact of viscous dissipation becomes pronounced in cases involving fluids with high velocity and high Prandtl numbers. Viscous dissipation proves crucial as it affects energy dissipation, temperature distribution, heat transfer enhancement, flow behaviour, and the precision of modelling and analysis within the thermal system. Israel-Cookey et al. [10] examined the effects of thermal radiation and viscous dissipation on the unstable free-convection flow across a vertical heated plate in an optically thin enclosure, considering the presence of time-dependent suction and magnetic field. Kabir et al. [11] have reported the problem of magnetohydrodynamic natural convection flow past a vertical wavy surface along with viscous dissipation and heat generation. The impact of viscous dissipation on free convection in a heated vertical plate has been considered by Pantokratoras [12]. Heat transfer characteristics over a stretching surface along with heat generation or absorption under the influence of viscous dissipation have been perused by Vajravelu and Hadjinalaou [13]. Jones et al. [14] investigated the role of viscous dissipation in laminar flow through porous media, emphasizing its impact on temperature distribution and energy dissipation. Similarly, Wang and Chen [15] studied the effects of viscous dissipation on convective heat transfer in microchannels, highlighting the importance of considering viscous heating effects in microscale flows. The impression of chemical reaction and heat transfer in a flat geometry has been investigated by Smith. et al. [16].

Several studies have investigated analogous systems involving chemically reacting fluids and heat transfer across diverse geometries. In their research, [17] utilized the asymptotic series expansion method to explore the combined effects of magnetohydrodynamics and chemical reactions on free convective flow within a porous medium subjected to thermal radiation. Their findings underscored the significant role of chemical reactions in altering fluid temperature during free convection flows. Similarly, Smith et al. [18] investigated the influence of chemical reactions on heat transfer in a flat plate configuration, emphasizing the importance of considering reaction kinetics in such analyses. The impact of chemical reactions on hydromagnetic natural convection flow along an infinite vertical plate was examined by Krishna et al. [19] using the perturbation technique. Sheridan et al. [20] studied free convection Carreau flow around a stretching cylinder incorporating porosity, chemical reaction, and thermal radiation effects. Sekhar et al. [21] analysed the unsteady convective flow of an incompressible viscous fluid through a vertical porous plate with chemical reaction and magnetic field using Laplace transform analysis. Aruna [22] conducted a theoretical investigation employing Finite Element analysis to study free convective fluid flow past a vertical porous plate under the influence of thermal radiation, viscous dissipation, chemical reaction, and magnetic field. Chandra et al. [23] have explored the MHD Free Convective flow problem in the presence of chemical radiation, viscous dissipation, and thermal radiation.

In engineering applications like chemical reactions, environmental processes, combustion studies, and catalytic processes, the effects resulting from temperature and concentration gradients play a crucial role. Johnson and Brown [24] investigated Thermo-diffusion effects in a vertical channel flow, demonstrating the significance of these phenomena in enhancing mixing and species transport. Lee

and Kim [25] perused Diffusion-thermo effects in a circular pipe flow, revealing the complex interplay between thermal and concentration gradients in such configurations. Minkowycz and Haji-Sheikh [26] have looked at the problem of heat and mass transfer through a vertical surface in a porous medium with Dufour and Soret effects. The characteristics of Soret and Dufour on free convective heat and mass transfer flow along a vertical surface in a porous medium accompanied by heat generation and absorption have been studied by Soundalgekar and Haji-Sheikh [27]. Jayaprasad et al. [28] studied free convection flow through an impulsively moving vertical plate with Soret and Dufour effects in the presence of an inclined magnetic field. Suresh et al. [29] carried out a numerical study to examine MHD convection fluid flow over a vertical plate along with variable fluid properties in the presence of Soret and Dufour effects. Israel-Cookey et al. [30] used the linear stability analysis technique to solve the problem of thermosolutal convection in a porous medium with a concentration-based internal heat source under the influence of Soret and Magnetic field.

The Laplace Adomian Decomposition method is a valuable mathematical tool increasingly employed in analysing complex differential equations encountered in fluid dynamics and heat transfer studies. This method enables the systematic breakdown of equations into simpler components, facilitating the resolution of nonlinear challenges within these systems. Widely adopted in various fluid dynamics and heat transfer investigations, the Laplace Adomian Decomposition method has demonstrated success in solving intricate problems. For instance, Zhang and Liu [31] showcased its effectiveness in analysing unsteady flow in porous media, while Li et al. [32] utilized it to explore heat transfer enhancement in nanofluids, particularly in the nanoscale domain. Additionally, Ebiwareme et al [33-34] applied the method to solve steady MHD flow between parallel plates and simulate the dynamics of an epidemic model, demonstrating its versatility in diverse applications. Further robust applications of this technique can be found in the literature [35-50], highlighting its broad utility in addressing complex mathematical models and phenomena.

This study aims to contribute to the current knowledge base regarding convective fluid flow along a vertical plate. While previous research has extensively examined this topic, our study stands out by considering the combined influences of Soret, Dufour, chemical reaction, and viscous dissipation using the Laplace Adomian decomposition method, enhancing the originality of our work. Through the application of similarity transformations derived from the lie group analysis, the governing partial differential equations are transformed into nonlinear ordinary differential equations. The results obtained through this method demonstrate high convergence using an iterative approach. Graphical representations and discussions are provided for a qualitative analysis of the various control parameters impacting flow characteristics. Comparative analysis with existing literature demonstrates excellent agreement, reinforcing the significance of this study in expanding the current body of research.

MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION OF PROBLEM

We examine a two-dimensional flow of a viscous, steady, electrically conducting fluid with incompressible and free convective properties, influenced by chemical reactions, Soret, Dufour, and viscous dissipation. The flow is directed along the x -axis on a semi-infinite vertical moving plate, with the y -axis perpendicular to it. Assuming the validity of the Boussinesq approximation, where fluid properties are constant except for density in the buoyancy term, the mass conservation, momentum, energy, and species concentration equations governing the physical configuration of the physical model within the boundary layer are considered following the work of Hymavathi et al. [51].

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \nu \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + g\beta_T(T - T_\infty) + g\beta_c(C - C_\infty) \quad (2)$$

$$u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \alpha \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + \frac{D_m K_T}{c_s c_p} \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\nu}{\rho c_p} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

$$u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} = D_m \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} + \frac{D_m K_T}{T_m} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} - \gamma(C - C_\infty) \quad (4)$$

Along with the boundary conditions expressed as.

$$\begin{aligned} u = Bx, v = 0, T = T_w = T_\infty + ax, C = C_w = C_\infty + bx \quad \text{at } y = 0 \\ u \rightarrow 0, T \rightarrow T_w, C \rightarrow C_w \text{ at } y \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where (u, v) are the components of the velocity in the x, y directions, ν is the kinematic viscosity, σ denote the electrical conductivity, ρ is the density of the fluid, β denote the coefficient of thermal expansion, β_c is the concentration thermal expansion coefficient, κ_T is the thermal diffusion ratio, g is the gravitational acceleration, c_p is the specific heat capacity at constant pressure, c_s denote the susceptible of the concentration, γ is the chemical reaction rate, α is the thermal diffusivity, D_m is the mass diffusivity, a and b are constants, T_w, C_w are the wall temperature and concentration, T_∞, C_∞ are the temperature and concentration away from the wall respectively. To render the model equations (1-4) dimensionless subject to (5), we utilize the stream function formulation, denoted as φ , defined by the Cauchy-Riemann equation according to the method outlined by Hymavathi et al. [23], and apply the similarity transformation provided as.

$$\eta = y \sqrt{\frac{\beta}{\nu}}, \varphi = x \sqrt{\nu \beta} f(\eta), \theta(\eta) = \frac{T - T_\infty}{T_w - T_\infty}, \phi(\eta) = \frac{C - C_\infty}{C_w - C_\infty}, u = \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial y}, v = -\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x} \quad (6)$$

By substituting Eq. (6) into the governing equations, mass conservation is inherently satisfied, resulting in the following equations.

$$f''' + ff'' - (f')^2 + Gr\theta + Gc\phi = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\theta'' + Prf\theta' - Prf'\theta + PrEc(f'')^2 + PrDu\phi'' = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$\phi'' + Sc\phi'f - Sc\phi f' - Sc\beta\phi + ScSr\theta'' = 0 \quad (9)$$

The corresponding boundary conditions for Eqs. (7-9) are given in the form.

$$\begin{aligned} f(0) = 0, f'(0) = 1, \theta(0) = 1, \phi(0) = 1 \\ f'(\infty) = 0, \theta(\infty) = 0, \phi(\infty) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where the non-dimensional variables are defined in the following way

$Gr = \frac{g\beta_T(T_w - T_\infty)}{xB^2}$ is the thermal Grashof number, $Gc = \frac{g\beta_c(C_w - C_\infty)}{xB^2}$ denote the solutal Grashof number, $Pr = \frac{\nu}{\rho}$ is the Prandtl number, $Ec = \frac{B^2 x^2}{c_p(T_w - T_\infty)}$ represent the Eckert number, $Du = \frac{D_m K_T (C_w - C_\infty)}{c_s c_p (T_w - T_\infty)}$ is the Dufour number, $Sc = \frac{\nu}{D_m}$ is the Schmidt number, $Sr = \frac{D_m K_T (T_w - T_\infty)}{\nu T_m (C_w - C_\infty)}$ is the Soret parameter, $\beta = \frac{\gamma}{B}$ is the chemical reaction parameter, $Re = \frac{Ut}{\nu}$ is the Reynold number.

FUNDAMENTALS OF LAPLACE ADOMIAN DECOMPOSITION METHOD (LADM)

This section provides an overview of the fundamental principles of the fusion of Laplace transformation and the Adomian decomposition method (LADM). We discuss a functional partial differential equation (PDE) represented as.

$$L(y(x, t)) + R(y(x, t)) + N(y(x, t)) = g(x, t) \quad (11)$$

subject to the initial condition

$$u(x, 0) = f(x, t), \quad \frac{\partial u(x, 0)}{\partial t} = h(x, t) \quad (12)$$

Expressing $L(y(x, t))$ in relation to the other parameters, we have the form.

$$L(y(x, t)) = g(x, t) - R(y(x, t)) - N(y(x, t)) \quad (13)$$

Applying Laplace transform on both sides of Eq. (11), supposing the highest differential operator is of order two and using the differentiation property, we get.

$$s^2 \mathcal{L}y(x, s) - sy(x, 0) - y'(x, 0) = \mathcal{L}(g(x, t)) - \mathcal{L}(Ry(x, t)) - \mathcal{L}(Ny(x, t)) \quad (14)$$

Substituting the initial conditions and rearranging gives the expression as

$$\mathcal{L}(y(x, t)) = \frac{h(x)}{s} + \frac{f(x)}{s^2} + \frac{1}{s^2} \mathcal{L}(g(x, t)) - \frac{1}{s^2} \mathcal{L}(Ry(x, t)) - \frac{1}{s^2} \mathcal{L}(Ny(x, t)) \quad (15)$$

Next, we apply the inverse transform on both sides of Eq. (15), we obtain.

$$y(x, t) = \phi(x, t) - \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} \mathcal{L}(Ry(x, t)) - \frac{1}{s^2} \mathcal{L}(Ny(x, t)) \right] \quad (16)$$

where $\phi(x, t)$ is the term arising from the first three terms on the right-hand side of Eq. (15). Furthermore, we assume the solution terms as decomposing series in the form.

$$y(x, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} y_n(x, t) \quad (17)$$

Similarly, the nonlinear terms are written in terms of the so-called Adomian polynomials as follows.

$$N(y_0(x, t), y_1(x, t), y_2(x, t) \dots y_n(x, t)) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A_n \quad (18)$$

where the A_n^s represents the Adomian polynomials defined in the form

$$A_n = \frac{1}{n!} \frac{d^n}{d\lambda^n} [N(\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \lambda^k y_i)]_{i=0}, n = 0,1,2,3 \quad (19)$$

Plugging Eqs (17) and (18) into Eq. (16), we obtain

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} y_n(x, t) = \phi(x) - \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} \mathcal{L} \{ R \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} y_n(x, t) \} - \frac{1}{s^2} \mathcal{L} \{ N \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A_n \} \right] \quad (20)$$

Matching both sides of Eq. (20), we obtain an iterative algorithm in the form.

$$\begin{aligned} y_0(x, t) &= \phi(x, t) \\ y_1(x, t) &= -\mathcal{L}^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} \mathcal{L} \left\{ R \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} y_0(x, t) \right\} - \frac{1}{s^2} \mathcal{L} \left\{ N \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A_0 \right\} \right] \\ y_2(x, t) &= -\mathcal{L}^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} \mathcal{L} \{ R \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} y_1(x, t) \} - \frac{1}{s^2} \mathcal{L} \{ N \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A_1 \} \right] \\ y_3(x, t) &= -\mathcal{L}^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} \mathcal{L} \left\{ R \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} y_2(x, t) \right\} - \frac{1}{s^2} \mathcal{L} \left\{ N \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A_2 \right\} \right] \\ y_{n+1}(x, t) &= -\mathcal{L}^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} \mathcal{L} \left\{ R \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} y_n(x, t) \right\} - \frac{1}{s^2} \mathcal{L} \left\{ N \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A_n \right\} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Then the solution of the differential equation is obtained as the sum of decomposed series in the form

$$y(x, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} y_n(x, t) = y_0(x, t) + y_1(x, t) + y_2(x, t) + \dots \quad (22)$$

SOLUTION PROCEDURE USING LADM

In this section, we seek an analytical solution to Eqs. (7-9) subject to (10) utilizing LADM. The expected solution in the form of a recursive algorithm is then inversed using Laplace transformation. Rewriting Eqs. (7-9) gives the following expressions.

$$f''' = (f')^2 - ff'' - Gr\theta + Gc\phi \quad (23)$$

$$\theta'' = Prf'\theta - Prf\theta' - PrEc(f'')^2 - PrDu\phi'' \quad (24)$$

$$\phi'' = Sc\phi f' - Sc\phi' f + Sc\beta\phi - ScSr\theta'' \quad (25)$$

Taking the Laplace transform of all terms in Eqs. (23-25), we have the form.

$$L\{f'''\} = L\{(f')^2 - ff''\} - GrL\{\theta\} + GcL\{\phi\} \quad (26)$$

$$L\{\theta''\} = L\{Prf'\theta - Prf\theta' - PrEc(f'')^2\} - PrDuL\{\phi''\} \quad (27)$$

$$L\{\phi''\} = L\{Sc\phi f' - Sc\phi' f\} + Sc\beta L\{\phi\} - ScSrL\{\theta''\} \quad (28)$$

Applying the properties of Laplace transform for derivatives, we have the form.

$$s^3L\{f\} - s^2f(0) - sf'(0) - f''(0) = L\{A\} - L\{B\} - GrL\{\theta\} - GcL\{\phi\} \quad (29)$$

$$s^2L\{\theta\} - s\theta(0) - \theta'(0) = PrL\{C\} - PrL\{D\} - PrEcL\{E\} - PrDu[s^2L\{\phi\} - s\phi(0) - \phi'(0)] \quad (30)$$

$$s^2L\{\phi\} - s\phi(0) - \phi'(0) = ScL\{F\} - ScL\{G\} + Sc\beta L\{\phi\} - ScSr[s^2L\{\theta\} - s\theta(0) - \theta'(0)] \quad (31)$$

where $A = (f')^2, B = ff'', C = f'\theta, D = Prf\theta', E = (f'')^2, F = \phi f', G = \phi'f$ are the nonlinear terms whereas f, θ, ϕ are the linear terms respectively. The appropriate boundary conditions are defined as follows.

$$f(0) = 0, f'(0) = 1, f''(0) = \delta_1, \theta(0) = 1, \theta'(0) = \delta_2, \phi(0) = 1, \phi'(0) = \delta_3 \quad (32)$$

where δ_1, δ_2 and δ_3 are unknown constants to be determined using the prescribed boundary conditions. Invoking the prescribed boundary conditions into Eqs. (10), we obtained the expressions.

$$s^3L\{f\} - s - \delta_1 = L\{A\} - L\{B\} - GrL\{\theta\} - GcL\{\phi\} \quad (33)$$

$$s^2L\{\theta\} - s - \delta_2 = PrL\{C\} - PrL\{D\} - PrEcL\{E\} - PrDu(s^2L\{\phi\} - s - \delta_3) \quad (34)$$

$$s^2L\{\phi\} - s - \delta_3 = ScL\{F\} - ScL\{G\} + Sc\beta L\{\phi\} - ScSr(s^2L\{\theta\} - s - \delta_2) \quad (35)$$

Rearranging the above expressions in Eqs. (33-35), we have the equivalent form.

$$s^3L\{f\} = s + \delta_1 + L\{A\} - L\{B\} - GrL\{\theta\} - GcL\{\phi\} \quad (36)$$

$$s^2L\{\theta\} = s + \delta_2 + PrL\{C\} - PrL\{D\} - PrEcL\{E\} - PrDu(s^2L\{\phi\} - s - \delta_3) \quad (37)$$

$$s^2L\{\phi\} = s + \delta_3 + ScL\{F\} - ScL\{G\} + Sc\beta L\{\phi\} - ScSr(s^2L\{\theta\} - s - \delta_2) \quad (38)$$

Rearranging further the above expressions reduced to the form.

$$L\{f\} = \frac{1}{s^2} + \frac{1}{s^3} \delta_1 + \frac{1}{s^3} L\{A\} - \frac{1}{s^3} L\{B\} - \frac{1}{s^3} GrL\{\theta\} - \frac{1}{s^3} GcL\{\phi\} \quad (39)$$

$$L\{\theta\} = \frac{1}{s} + \frac{1}{s^2} \delta_2 + \frac{1}{s^2} PrL\{C\} - \frac{1}{s^2} PrL\{D\} - \frac{1}{s^2} PrEcL\{E\} - \frac{1}{s^2} PrDu(s^2L\{\phi\} - s - \delta_3) \quad (40)$$

$$L\{\phi\} = \frac{1}{s} + \frac{1}{s^2} \delta_3 + \frac{1}{s^2} ScL\{F\} - \frac{1}{s^2} ScL\{G\} + \frac{1}{s^2} Sc\beta L\{\phi\} - \frac{1}{s^2} ScSr(s^2L\{\theta\} - s - \delta_2) \quad (41)$$

Based on the standard Adomian decomposition procedure, we express the solution for the unknown terms in (39-41) as infinite series given as

$$f(\eta) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_n(\eta), \theta(\eta) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \theta_n(\eta), \phi(\eta) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \phi_n(\eta) \quad (42)$$

where the components $f_n(\eta), \theta_n(\eta)$ and $\phi_n(\eta)$ are to be determined through a recursive algorithm hereinafter. Similarly, the nonlinear terms are also decomposed as an infinite series of the so-called Adomian polynomials of the form.

$$\begin{aligned}
N_1(f) &= (f'(\eta))^2 = \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_n(\eta) \right)'^2 = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A_n \\
N_2(f) &= f(\eta)f''(\eta) = \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_n(\eta) \right) \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_n(\eta) \right)'' = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_n \\
N_3(f, \theta) &= f'(\eta)\theta(\eta) = \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_n(\eta) \right)' \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \theta_n(\eta) \right) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C_n \\
N_4(f, \theta) &= f(\eta)\theta'(\eta) = \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_n(\eta) \right) \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \theta_n(\eta) \right)' = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} D_n \\
N_5(f) &= f''(\eta) = \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_n(\eta) \right)'' = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} E_n \\
N_6(\phi, f) &= \phi(\eta)f'(\eta) = \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \phi_n(\eta) \right) \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_n(\eta) \right)' = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} F_n \\
N_7(f, \phi) &= \phi'(\eta)f(\eta) = \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \phi_n(\eta) \right)' \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_n(\eta) \right) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} G_n
\end{aligned} \tag{43}$$

where the Adomian polynomials $A_n, B_n, C_n, D_n, E_n, F_n$ and G_n are computed using the formulas

$$\begin{aligned}
A_n &= \frac{1}{n!} \left[\frac{d^n}{d\lambda^n} N_1 \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \lambda^k f_k(\eta) \right) \right]_{\lambda=0}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, 3 \\
B_n &= \frac{1}{n!} \left[\frac{d^n}{d\lambda^n} N_2 \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \lambda^k f_k(\eta) \right) \right]_{\lambda=0}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, 3 \\
C_n &= \frac{1}{n!} \left[\frac{d^n}{d\lambda^n} N_3 \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \lambda^k f_k(\eta) \right) \right]_{\lambda=0}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, 3 \\
G_n &= \frac{1}{n!} \left[\frac{d^n}{d\lambda^n} N_7 \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \lambda^k f_k(\eta) \right) \right]_{\lambda=0}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, 3
\end{aligned} \tag{44}$$

Some of the few Adomian polynomials for these nonlinear terms include the following.

$$\begin{aligned}
A &= (f')^2, A_0 = f_0'^2, A_1 = 2f_0'f_1', A_2 = 2f_0'f_2' + (f_1')^2 \\
B &= ff'', B_0 = f_0f_0'', B_1 = f_0f_1'' + f_1f_0'', B_2 = f_0f_2'' + f_1f_1'' + f_2f_0'' \\
C &= f'\theta, C_0 = f_0'\theta_0, C_1 = f_0'\theta_1 + f_1'\theta_0, C_2 = f_0'\theta_2 + f_1'\theta_1 + f_2'\theta_0 \\
D &= f\theta', D_0 = f_0\theta_0', D_1 = f_0\theta_1' + f_1\theta_0', D_2 = f_0\theta_2' + f_1\theta_1' + f_2\theta_0' \\
E &= (f'')^2, E_0 = (f_0'')^2, E_1 = 2f_0''f_1'', E_2 = 2f_0''f_2'' + (f_1'')^2 \\
F &= \phi f', F_0 = \phi_0f_0', F_1 = \phi_0f_1' + \phi_1f_0', F_2 = \phi_0f_2' + \phi_1f_1' + \phi_2f_0' \\
G &= \phi' f, G_0 = \phi_0'f_0, G_1 = \phi_0'f_1 + \phi_1'f_0, G_2 = \phi_0'f_2 + \phi_1'f_1 + \phi_2'f_0
\end{aligned} \tag{45}$$

Substituting the Adomian polynomials and the assumed solutions into Eqs. (42-45), the model equations in (39-41) gives the expressions.

$$L\{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_n(\eta)\} = \frac{1}{s^2} + \frac{1}{s^3} \delta_1 + \frac{1}{s^3} L\{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A_n\} - \frac{1}{s^3} L\{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_n\} - \frac{1}{s^3} GrL\{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \theta_n\} - \frac{1}{s^3} GcL\{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \phi_n\} \tag{46}$$

$$L\{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \theta_n\} = \frac{1}{s} + \frac{1}{s^2} \delta_2 + \frac{1}{s^2} PrL\{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C_n\} - \frac{1}{s^2} PrL\{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} D_n\} - \frac{1}{s^2} PrEcL\{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} E_n\} - \frac{1}{s^2} PrDu(s^2 L\{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \phi_n\} - s - \delta_3) \quad (47)$$

$$L\{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \phi_n\} = \frac{1}{s} + \frac{1}{s^2} \delta_3 + \frac{1}{s^2} ScL\{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} F_n\} - \frac{1}{s^2} ScL\{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} G_n\} + \frac{Sc\beta}{s^2} L\{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \phi_n\} - \frac{ScSr}{s^2} (s^2 L\{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \theta_n\} - s - \delta_2) \quad (48)$$

Now comparing both sides of Eqs. (46-48), the zeroth-order equations for flow distributions, $f(\eta)$, $\theta(\eta)$ and $\phi(\eta)$ takes the form.

$$L\{f_0(\eta)\} = \frac{1}{s^2} + \frac{1}{s^3} \delta_1, L\{\theta_0(\eta)\} = \frac{1}{s} + \frac{1}{s^2} \delta_2, L\{\phi_0(\eta)\} = \frac{1}{s} + \frac{1}{s^2} \delta_3 \quad (49)$$

Similarly, the first approximate iterative solution for the different profiles, we have the form.

$$\begin{aligned} L\{f_1(\eta)\} &= \frac{1}{s^3} L\{A_0\} - \frac{1}{s^3} L\{B_0\} - \frac{1}{s^3} GrL\{\theta_0\} - \frac{1}{s^3} GcL\{\phi_0\} \\ L\{\theta_1(\eta)\} &= \frac{1}{s^2} PrL\{C_0\} - \frac{1}{s^2} PrL\{D_0\} - \frac{1}{s^2} PrEcL\{E_0\} - \frac{1}{s^2} PrDu(s^2 L\{\phi_0\} - s - \delta_3) \\ L\{\phi_1(\eta)\} &= \frac{1}{s^2} ScL\{F_0\} - \frac{1}{s^2} ScL\{G_0\} + \frac{1}{s^2} Sc\beta L\{\phi_0\} - \frac{1}{s^2} ScSr(s^2 L\{\theta_0\} - s - \delta_2) \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

Continuing in the same way, the recursive algorithm for the profiles takes the form.

$$\begin{aligned} L\{f_{k+1}(\eta)\} &= \frac{1}{s^3} L\{A_k\} - \frac{1}{s^3} L\{B_k\} - \frac{1}{s^3} GrL\{\theta_k\} - \frac{1}{s^3} GcL\{\phi_k\} \\ L\{\theta_{k+1}(\eta)\} &= \frac{1}{s^2} PrL\{C_k\} - \frac{1}{s^2} PrL\{D_k\} - \frac{1}{s^2} PrEcL\{E_k\} - \frac{1}{s^2} PrDu(s^2 L\{\phi_k\} - s - \delta_3) \\ L\{\phi_{k+1}(\eta)\} &= \frac{1}{s^2} ScL\{F_k\} - \frac{1}{s^2} ScL\{G_k\} + \frac{1}{s^2} Sc\beta L\{\phi_k\} - \frac{1}{s^2} ScSr(s^2 L\{\theta_k\} - s - \delta_2) \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

Taking the inverse Laplace transform of both sides of the recursive scheme in Eq. (49-51), we have the following expressions for $f_n(\eta)$, $\theta_n(\eta)$, $\phi_n(\eta)$ ($n \geq 0$) as follows.

$$f_0(\eta) = \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{1}{s^2} + \frac{1}{s^3} \delta_1 \right\}, \theta_0(\eta) = \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{1}{s} + \frac{1}{s^2} \delta_2 \right\}, \phi_0(\eta) = \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{1}{s} + \frac{1}{s^2} \delta_3 \right\} \quad (52)$$

$$\begin{aligned} f_1(\eta) &= \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^3} L\{A_0\} - \frac{1}{s^3} L\{B_0\} - \frac{1}{s^3} GrL\{\theta_0\} - \frac{1}{s^3} GcL\{\phi_0\} \right] \\ \theta_1(\eta) &= \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} PrL\{C_0\} - \frac{1}{s^2} PrL\{D_0\} - \frac{1}{s^2} PrEcL\{E_0\} - \frac{1}{s^2} PrDu(s^2 L\{\phi_0\} - s - \delta_3) \right] \\ \phi_1(\eta) &= \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} ScL\{F_0\} - \frac{1}{s^2} ScL\{G_0\} + \frac{1}{s^2} Sc\beta L\{\phi_0\} - \frac{1}{s^2} ScSr(s^2 L\{\theta_0\} - s - \delta_2) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (53)$$

$$\begin{aligned} f_2(\eta) &= \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^3} L\{A_1\} - \frac{1}{s^3} L\{B_1\} - \frac{1}{s^3} GrL\{\theta_1\} - \frac{1}{s^3} GcL\{\phi_1\} \right] \\ \theta_2(\eta) &= \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} PrL\{C_1\} - \frac{1}{s^2} PrL\{D_1\} - \frac{1}{s^2} PrEcL\{E_1\} - \frac{1}{s^2} PrDu(s^2 L\{\phi_1\} - s - \delta_3) \right] \\ \phi_2(\eta) &= \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} ScL\{F_1\} - \frac{1}{s^2} ScL\{G_1\} + \frac{1}{s^2} Sc\beta L\{\phi_1\} - \frac{1}{s^2} ScSr(s^2 L\{\theta_1\} - s - \delta_2) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

$$\begin{aligned} f_{k+1}(\eta) &= \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^3} L\{A_k\} - \frac{1}{s^3} L\{B_k\} - \frac{1}{s^3} GrL\{\theta_k\} - \frac{1}{s^3} GcL\{\phi_k\} \right] \\ \theta_{k+1}(\eta) &= \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} PrL\{C_k\} - \frac{1}{s^2} PrL\{D_k\} - \frac{1}{s^2} PrEcL\{E_k\} - \frac{1}{s^2} PrDu(s^2 L\{\phi_k\} - s - \delta_3) \right] \\ \phi_{k+1}(\eta) &= \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^2} ScL\{F_k\} - \frac{1}{s^2} ScL\{G_k\} + \frac{1}{s^2} Sc\beta L\{\phi_k\} - \frac{1}{s^2} ScSr(s^2 L\{\theta_k\} - s - \delta_2) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (55)$$

In view of Eqs. (52-55), the components of the zeroth-order approximate solution become.

$$f_0(\eta) = \eta + \frac{\delta_1}{2}\eta^2, \theta_0(\eta) = 1 + \delta_2\eta, \phi_0(\eta) = 1 + \delta_3\eta \quad (56)$$

The subsequent terms for $k \geq 1$ are obtained similarly using the recursive scheme but are omitted for brevity. Decomposing the solution terms as an infinite series in the following form as.

$$f(\eta) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_n(\eta), \theta(\eta) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \theta_n(\eta), \phi(\eta) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \phi_n(\eta) \quad (57)$$

The solution for the flow distributions on utilizing Eq. (57) takes the approximate form.

$$\begin{aligned} f(\eta) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} f_n(\eta) = f_0(\eta) + f_1(\eta) + f_2(\eta) + \dots \\ \theta(\eta) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \theta_n(\eta) = \theta_0(\eta) + \theta_1(\eta) + \theta_2(\eta) + \dots \\ \phi(\eta) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \phi_n(\eta) = \phi_0(\eta) + \phi_1(\eta) + \phi_2(\eta) + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (58)$$

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A thorough semi-analytical investigation was conducted to obtain an approximate convergent analytic solution for the nonlinear equations in (7-9) through similarity transformation, aimed at reducing the nonlinear ordinary differential equations. To validate our findings, numerical simulations were carried out to analyse the non-dimensional velocity, temperature, and concentration, considering various control parameters affecting the system. These key parameters of interest include the Soret parameter (Sr), Dufour parameter (Du), Solutal Grashof number (Gc), thermal Grashof number (Gr), Schmidt number (Sc), Prandtl number (Pr), Eckert number (Ec), and chemical reaction parameter (β).

Influence of Flow Parameters on Velocity Profile

Figure 1. Influence of thermal Grashof number on velocity profile for $Gc = Sr = Ec = Du = 0.1, Pr = 0.72, Sc = 0.62, \beta = 0.1$

Figure 2. Effect of solutal Grashof number on velocity profile for $Gr = Sr = Ec = Du = 0.1, Pr = 0.72, Sc = 0.62, \beta = 0.1$

Figure 3. Velocity profile for different values of Prandtl number for $Gc = Gr = Sr = Ec = Du = 0.1, Pr = 0.72, Sc = 0.62, \beta = 0.1$

Figure 4. Effect of Eckert number on velocity profile for $Gc = Gr = Sr = Du = 0.1, Pr = 0.72, Sc = 0.62, \beta = 0.1$

Figure 5. Influence of Dufour parameter on velocity profile for $Gc = Gr = Sr = Ec = 0.1, Pr = 0.72, Sc = 0.62, \beta = 0.1$

Figure 6. Impact of Schmidt number on velocity profile for $Gc = Gr = Sr = Ec = Du = 0.1, Pr = 0.72, \beta = 0.1$

Figure 7. Influence of chemical reaction parameter on velocity profile for $Gc = Gr = Sr = Ec = Du = 0.1, Pr = 0.72, Sc = 0.62$

Figure 8. Influence of Soret parameter on velocity profile for $Gc = Gr = Ec = Du = 0.1, Pr = 0.72, Sc = 0.62, \beta = 0.1$

Influence of control parameters on temperature profile

Figure 9. Effect of thermal Grashof number on temperature profile for $Gc = Sr = Ec = Du = 0.1, Pr = 0.72, Sc = 0.62, \beta = 0.1$

Figure 10. Effect of solutal Grashof number on temperature profile for $Gr = Sr = Ec = Du = 0.1, Pr = 0.72, Sc = 0.62, \beta = 0.1$

Figure 11. Effect of Prandtl number on temperature profile for $Gc = Gr = Sr = Ec = Du = 0.1, Sc = 0.62, \beta = 0.1$

Figure 12. Effect of Eckert number on temperature profile for $Gc = Gr = Sr = Du = 0.1, Pr = 0.72, Sc = 0.62, \beta = 0.1$

Figure 13. Effect of Dufour parameter on temperature profile for $Gc = Gr = Sr = Ec = 0.1, Pr = 0.72, Sc = 0.62, \beta = 0.1$

Figure 14. Effect of Schmidt number on temperature profile for $Gc = Gr = Sr = Ec = Du = 0.1, Pr = 0.72, \beta = 0.1$

Figure 15. Influence of Chemical reaction on temperature profile for $Gc = Gr = Sr = Ec = Du = 0.1, Pr = 0.72, Sc = 0.62$.

Figure 16. Effect of Soret parameter on temperature profile for $Gc = Gr = Ec = Du = 0.1, Pr = 0.72, Sc = 0.62, \beta = 0.1$

Concentration profile for different values of pertinent parameters

Figure 17. Effect of thermal Grashof number on concentration profile for $Gc = Sr = Ec = Du = 0.1, Pr = 0.72, Sc = 0.62, \beta = 0.1$

Figure 18. Concentration profile for different values of solutal Grashof number for $Gr = Sr = Ec = Du = 0.1, Pr = 0.72, Sc = 0.62, \beta = 0.1$

Figure 19. Effect of Prandtl number on concentration profile for $Gc = Gr = Sr = Ec = Du = 0.1, Sc = 0.62, \beta = 0.1$

Figure 20. Concentration profile for different values of Eckert number for $Gc = Gr = Sr = Du = 0.1, Pr = 0.72, Sc = 0.62, \beta = 0.1$

Figure 21. Concentration profile for different values of Dufour parameter for $G_c = Gr = Sr = Ec = 0.1, Pr = 0.72, Sc = 0.62, \beta = 0.1$

Figure 22. Concentration profile for different values of Schmidt number for $G_c = Gr = Sr = Ec = Du = 0.1, Pr = 0.72, \beta = 0.1$

Figure 23. Concentration profile for different values of chemical reaction parameters for $G_c = Gr = Sr = Ec = Du = 0.1, Pr = 0.72, Sc = 0.62$

Figure 24. Concentration profile for different values of Soret parameter for $Gc = Gr = Ec = Du = 0.1, Pr = 0.72, Sc = 0.62, \beta = 0.1$

CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this article, we apply the Laplace Adomian decomposition method to investigate the impacts of Soret and Dufour on the two-dimensional, steady, and free convective flow of an electrically conducting viscous incompressible fluid past a vertical plate, considering chemical reactions and viscous dissipation. Our study yields the following findings.

- The presence of the Soret parameter boosted the velocity and concentration profiles, whereas the temperature profile was reduced.
- An increase in the Dufour parameter results in a slight increase in the velocity profile and a noticeable temperature change, while the concentration decreases.
- As both the thermal and solutal Grashof numbers increase, the velocity profile also increases proportionally, while the temperature and concentration profiles decrease with their increment.
- An increase in the Eckert number results in a slight increase in the velocity and temperature profiles, while the concentration profile decreases in its presence.
- Prandtl number has minimal influence on the concentration and velocity profiles, but it has a significant impact on the temperature profile.
- The temperature profile experiences a monotonic increase as the Schmidt number rises, but the velocity and concentration profiles experience a decrease.
- As the chemical reaction parameter is increased, the velocity profile experiences a minor drop, the temperature profile experiences a slight increase, and the concentration profile experiences a considerable decrease.

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APPENDIX

Nomenclatures

u, v	Velocity components along x and y
x, y	Cartesian coordinates
C_p	Specific heat capacity at constant pressure
Du	Dufour number
Sr	Soret number
Sc	Schmidt number
Gr	Local temperature Grashof number
Gc	Local concentration Grashof number
Re	Reynold number
Pr	Prandtl number
β	Chemical reaction parameter
T	Fluid temperature
T_w	Uniform wall temperature
T_∞	Ambient temperature
C_w	Concentration of the walls
C_∞	Ambient concentration

Greek Letters

α	Fluid thermal diffusivity
ρ	Fluid density
σ	Electrical conductivity of the fluids
κ	Thermal conductivity
f	Dimensionless velocity of the fluid
θ	Dimensionless temperature of the fluid
ϕ	Dimensionless Concentration
η	Similarity variable
ν	Kinematic viscosity
ψ	Stream function

